

CREATIVE PEDAGOGY IN TECHNOLOGICAL EDUCATION AS A PRIORITY DIRECTION OF MODERN PEDAGOGY

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Annotation: This article highlights the fact that the science of creative pedagogy is one of the priorities of modern pedagogy, as well as the importance of developing creative qualities in a person.

Keywords: "Creative pedagogy", series of sciences, innovative, professional maturity, ontogenesis, methodological ideas, socio-economic, integration, continuity, succession, department of education, stimulus, specific, observation, original ideas, strategy.

Аннотация: В данной статье подчеркивается тот факт, что наука творческая педагогика является одним из приоритетов современной педагогики, а также важность развития творческих качеств в личности.

Ключевые слова: «Креативная педагогика», серия наук, инновация, профессиональная зрелость, онтогенез, методологические идеи, социально-экономические, интеграция, преемственность, преемственность, отдел образования, стимул, специфика, наблюдение, оригинальные идеи, стратегия.

It was not so long ago that the concept of "Creative pedagogy" began to be used in modern pedagogy. However, the need to find innovative and creative approaches to the teaching process ensured the formation of "Creative pedagogy" as an independent subject among pedagogical disciplines. The basis of this subject is the history of pedagogy, general and professional pedagogy, and methodological ideas of such disciplines as psychology, teaching methodology of special subjects, educational technology, and professional ethics. Professional growth and

development of a person as a specialist is manifested as a process. Professional maturity is an important period of human ontogeny, starting from professional growth, development ideas (14-17 years old) and ending professional activity (55-60 years old).

The formation and development of a creative person depends on the mutual compatibility of changes in his inner and outer world, socio-economic conditions, and human ontogenesis - from birth to the end of his life, the content of activity that requires continuity and succession. The pace and scope of this process depends on biological and social factors, the activity and creative qualities of a person, as well as existing conditions, vital and professional events. In modern conditions, it is necessary for a pedagogue to have the qualities of creativity.

Literature analysis. Educational system management bodies focus on achieving high efficiency in educational institutions every year. For this purpose, the curriculum is developed, new textbooks are created. This helps both students and teachers to grow professionally. Conducted practical actions create the need for achievement and progress in students to a certain extent, help to develop their learning abilities to some extent.

However, by the end of the academic year, there are no high-level positive results in students' mastery of subjects in higher education institutions. Many students have lost interest in learning. As a result, teachers are not thinking about organizing professional activity with pleasure as before. Although the governing bodies of the educational system have set new measures to change the activities of students who do not want to learn, and teachers who do not want to teach such learners, the situation remains unchanged. What is the reason for this? Maybe the pre-planned lessons are not interesting for the students, maybe the fact that the educational content is set in a certain pattern does not give any stimulus or incentive for the students. Abandoning pre-planning of educational activities, formation and

development of critical, creative thinking in students, forcing them to think creatively, come up with new ideas is the main factor in changing the attitude to education, encouraging them to achieve achievements. The missing factor in training is creativity.

Result. To fully understand the general nature of the process of developing creative qualities in a person, it is necessary to first understand the meaning of the concept of "creativity". The concept of "creativity" reflects cultural diversity. For Westerners, creativity is generally considered a novelty. They emphasize that creativity is based on unconventionality, curiosity, imagination, humor, and freedom.

Easterners, on the other hand, understand creativity as a process of rebirth of goodness. Although Westerners and Easterners have different views on creativity, representatives of both cultures highly value this quality and its possession. According to Patti Drapeau, creative thinking is, above all, comprehensive thinking about a particular issue. Multidisciplinary thinking requires students to draw on multiple ideas when completing assignments, problems, and tasks. In contrast, one-sided thinking refers to focusing on only one true idea.

In observation, one can not deny one of the one-sided and many-sided thinking on the matter. Therefore, one and comprehensive thinking is equally important in the formation of creativity. That is, when completing a task, solving a problem, the student looks for several options for a solution (multidirectional thinking), and then stops at the only correct solution that guarantees the most optimal result (unidirectional thinking).

Based on the above-mentioned ideas, the concept of "creativity" can be interpreted as follows: Creativity (lat., ing. "create" - creation, "creative" - creator) is a creative element that describes the readiness of an individual to produce new ideas and is part of talent as an independent factor. ability.

A person's creativity is manifested in his thinking, communication, feelings, and certain types of activities. Creativity describes a person as a whole or his specific characteristics. Creativity is also reflected as an important factor of talent. In addition, creativity determines mental acuity, "ensures the active involvement of students in the educational process

The problem of increasing creative and creative abilities of students in the process of teaching is complex and multifaceted. Therefore, it is important to develop students' interest and ability in national handicrafts and academic subjects in improving their scientific-theoretical and practical knowledge.

Developing creative qualities in a person is a complex process. For this, it is appropriate to organize activities of a creative nature in the teaching of "Technological education". Such activities increase the interest of students and encourage them to do more.

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In recent years, this situation has been expressed by the concept of "pedagogical creativity". Creative thinking can be clearly reflected in every social sphere, and the teacher's creativity is reflected in his creative approach to the organization of professional activities organized by him. In recent years, this situation is expressed by the concept of "pedagogical creativity".

Pedagogical creativity - defines the ability of a pedagogue to create new ideas that serve to ensure the effectiveness of the educational process, as well as to positively solve existing pedagogical problems, unlike traditional pedagogical thinking. Due to the teacher's lack of creativity, students have interesting and wonderful ideas, but they are slow to express them. For this reason, the methods

used in the educational process are determined by the fact that they do not serve to form the skills of free, independent thinking in students.

The tools and strategies recommended by the author are useful for teachers in developing students' creativity and develop students' interest and desire to learn academic subjects. The creativity of the pedagogue in professional activity is manifested in various forms.

Summary. Therefore, "Creative pedagogy" must be able to guarantee the following two conditions:

1. Attracting the attention of students who have low mastery of academic subjects and who consider their study boring by teachers to master the basics of science;

2. To create an opportunity for teachers to use them effectively in the audience by recommending strategies and tools that serve to stimulate creative thinking and creative activity results in students.

The science of "Creative pedagogy" serves to create the necessary conditions for professional development of future specialists.

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